

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	840.347(18)	840.347(18)
Space group	P 21/n	P 21/n
Hall group	-P 2yn	-P 2yn
Moiety formula	C9 H7 N3 O2	?
Sum formula	C9 H7 N3 O2	C9 H7 N3 O2
Mr	189.18	189.18
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.495	1.495
Z	4	4
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.110	0.110
F000	392.0	392.0
F000'	392.18	
h, k, lmax	13, 14, 33	0, 0, 0
Nref	7098	7081
Tmin, Tmax	0.956, 0.974	0.847, 1.000
Tmin'	0.953	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.847 Tmax=1.000
AbsCorr = NONE

Data completeness= 0.998 Theta(max)= 45.464

R(reflections)= 0.0330(6420) wR2(reflections)=
0.1033(7081)

S = 1.047 Npar= 127

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format
test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.
Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

 Alert level C

PLAT977_ALERT_2_C Check Negative Difference Density on H1 . -0.35 eA-3

 Alert level G

PLAT005_ALERT_5_G No Embedded Refinement Details Found in the CIF Please Do !
PLAT007_ALERT_5_G Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms 1 Report
H1
PLAT143_ALERT_4_G s.u. on c - Axis Small or Missing 0.00010 Ang.
PLAT153_ALERT_1_G The s.u.'s on the Cell Axes are Equal ..(Note) 0.0001 Ang.
PLAT883_ALERT_1_G Absent Datum for _atom_sites_solution_primary .. Please Do !
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 17 Note
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 2.863 Note
Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 3.61 or SHELX Weight 9.87
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 8 Info
PLAT992_ALERT_5_G Repd & Actual _reflns_number_gt Values Differ by 2 Check

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
 0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
 1 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
 9 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

2 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
 2 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
 0 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
 2 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
 4 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

Datablock: iii_IAM

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0007 A Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=8.9369(1) b=7.1050(2) c=16.1335(1)
 alpha=90 beta=97.740(1) gamma=90

Temperature: 110 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1015.09(3)	1015.091(13)
Space group	P 21/c	P 21/c
Hall group	-P 2ybc	-P 2ybc
Moiety formula	C18 H14 Cl2 Cu N6 O4	?
Sum formula	C18 H14 Cl2 Cu N6 O4	C18 H14 Cl2 Cu N6 O4
Mr	512.80	512.80
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.678	1.678
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	1.379	1.379
F000	518.0	518.0
F000'	519.40	
h, k, lmax	17, 14, 32	0, 0, 0
Nref	8579	8569
Tmin, Tmax	0.738, 0.813	0.972, 0.985
Tmin'	0.570	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.972 Tmax=0.985
 AbsCorr = NONE

Data completeness= 0.999 Theta(max)= 45.463

R(reflections)= 0.0203(7768)

wR2(reflections)=
 0.0582(8569)

S = 1.077

Npar= 142

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

 Alert level B

PLAT934_ALERT_3_B Number of (Iobs-Icalc)/Sigma(W) > 10 Outliers .. 3 Check
4 1 3, 0 3 4, 1 1 7,

 Alert level C

PLAT094_ALERT_2_C Ratio of Maximum / Minimum Residual Density 2.18 Report

 Alert level G

PLAT005_ALERT_5_G No Embedded Refinement Details Found in the CIF Please Do !
PLAT007_ALERT_5_G Number of Unrefined Donor-H Atoms 1 Report
H1
PLAT143_ALERT_4_G s.u. on c - Axis Small or Missing 0.00010 Ang.
PLAT152_ALERT_1_G The Supplied and Calc. Volume s.u. Differ by ... 17 Units
PLAT232_ALERT_2_G Hirshfeld Test Diff (M-X) Cul --N3 . 13.0 s.u.
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G Tentative Bond Valency for Cul (II) . 2.14 Info
PLAT883_ALERT_1_G Absent Datum for _atom_sites_solution_primary .. Please Do !
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600 9 Note
PLAT969_ALERT_5_G The 'Henn et al.' R-Factor-gap value 1.591 Note
Predicted wR2: Based on SigI**2 3.66 or SHELX Weight 5.41
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density. 8 Info

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2 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
4 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check
-
-

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

